

Active transient cooling by magnetocaloric materials

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Abstract:

The magnetocaloric effect (MCE) has been intensively studied for novel energy efficient thermal management systems. The present study demonstrates a proof-of-concept magnetic cooling setup for active cooling of the thermal spikes of a heated resistor. It was demonstrated that the thermal spikes could be actively cooled. Using Gd as the MCE material, the device was capable of actively cooling thermal spikes within one cycle since the dynamics of magnetic phase transition in Gd (a second-order magnetic phase transition material) are favorable to effect a fast MCE response. Enhanced cooling rate of the heated resistor of up to ~85% for active cooling by MCE compared to passive cooling was achieved. The cooling curve of the resistor was found to follow an exponential decrease. Our results show that magnetic cooling systems can be useful in active transient cooling.

Keywords: magnetocaloric materials; thermal management; active cooling

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1 Introduction

Thermal management methods are required in an enormous range of applications, e.g., to heat and cool buildings (which contributes significantly to global energy consumption) [1-3], for electronic and photonic components [4-8], as well as refrigeration [9, 10]. Cooling technologies in buildings account for ~40% of global energy consumption and are of high significance in reducing thermal discomfort in regions with a hot climate and high humidity [2, 11-13]. This prompts for urgency to lower energy consumption using novel, energy efficient, active and passive cooling techniques. Since passive cooling involves thermal management of the load without utilization of a power-consuming mechanical apparatus, active cooling is a superior alternative in cooling buildings [2]. Today's major cooling systems are mainly electrically driven compression chillers, which exhibit an average coefficient of performance in the range of 3.0 – 5.0 [14]. For warm climates, peak energy demand in cooling buildings are typically more significant during daytime compared to night [2]. This is due to the operational inefficiencies resulted from the diverse energy demands in different climates or geological locations; active thermal management systems, which exploit phase change materials (PCM), display promising solution.

Thermal management techniques have also been proposed to cool electronic devices or mitigate transient local heat spikes resulting from “hot spots” in these devices [4-8]. Unavoidable heat generation, during the normal operation of electronic devices, when in excess can drastically reduce reliability and performance of these devices, as well as lowering the signal to noise ratio. Advances in technology demand improved power performance in electronic systems, consequently increasing with a challenging pace the performance requirements of cooling system needs. Hence, novel cooling systems need to be considered to cool future high power electronic systems [4-8]. Transient local heat spikes resulting from hot spots in these devices are not adequately mitigated by conventional steady state based cooling systems. Transient heat spikes should be thermally managed as and when they occur to allow the temperature to be maintained below a predefined maximum temperature, but this cannot be readily achieved by the usual heat transfer methods such as air fans or continuous liquid flows.

Heat absorption or discharge can be readily attained when a PCM undergoes a phase change [14]. PCM have shown promise for temperature control applications when integrated into thermal management system. However, the low thermal conductivities and losses associated with incongruent melting and solidification during phase transitions of conventional PCM are major limitations [3, 14]. A potential solution to these pressing issues is magnetic cooling

systems, based on the magnetocaloric effect (MCE) displayed during magnetic and/or structural phase transformations. The recent development of magnetic cooling devices provides a superior alternative to conventional vapor-compression refrigeration technology due to its high energy efficiency (cooling efficiency has been demonstrated to reach 60% of theoretical limit while only ~45% can be attained in the best vapor-compression refrigerators [15] and suggested it could attain up to 80% of Carnot limit using a single stage refrigerator with an magnetocaloric material (MCM) with negligible hysteresis [16]), environmental friendliness, absence of compressor etc.[17].

Magnetic cooling systems are based on the MCE, an intrinsic thermomagnetic phenomenon which describes a temperature change induced in magnetic materials when they are adiabatically subjected to a varying applied magnetic field (**Fig. 1**). The entropy of a magnetic material consists of contributions from its lattice as well as from its electronic and magnetic spins. Upon adiabatic application of an external magnetic field (H), the magnetic spins align parallel to H , causing the magnetic component of the entropy to decrease. The lattice entropy consequently increases, leading to a temperature rise in the material. This induced heat can be expelled by a heat transfer medium, causing the material to return to the ambient temperature. When the material is adiabatically demagnetized, it cools below ambient temperature due to an increase in disorder of the magnetic spins, which results in lower lattice entropy. MCE based devices can offer improved energy efficiency, low noise, compact configuration [18], operational cost savings (it eliminates the compressor which is the most inefficient part of the refrigerator) [15] and environmental friendliness (no hazardous/ozone depleting gases are involved), which addresses critical issues in facing conventional cooling systems.

Fig. 1 Schematic representation of a magnetic cooling cycle (after [28]).

MCE, which is the phenomenon governing magnetic cooling [19-23], has been recently proposed to exhibit good potential for use in computer cooling systems [24, 25]. The transient response of magnetic refrigeration systems has rarely been reported [26, 27] and active cooling by MCE has not been reported so far. Since MCE exploits the adiabatic temperature change accompanying a magnetic phase transition of a magnetic material to induce temperature change, it can overcome some of the limitations of conventional PCM used in thermal management systems. In this paper, we show that active transient magnetic cooling can be achieved.

To demonstrate active transient cooling of a heated electrical resistor by MCE, a proof-of-concept setup was designed and developed. The setup consists of a resistor (heater), Gd block, thermocouples and polystyrene insulation (**Fig. 2**). The magnetic field was applied by an electromagnet, providing a maximum magnetic field of 16 kOe. Active cooling of thermal spikes using a benchmark MCE material (Gd) was investigated. To study conduction cooling by MCE, the resistor and Gd block were mounted in direct contact using nonmagnetic thermocouple wires to measure the time dependence of temperatures of the resistor, Gd and their interface. The influence of different heating power inputs of the resistor (1 We5 W) on the cooling behavior was studied.

Fig. 2 Schematic representation of transient cooling setup. The cross-section of the magnetocaloric cooled resistor cell is also schematically highlighted in the yellow region.

In actual systems, the magnetic cooling system will be placed away from the electronic devices and cooled by airflow from the magnetic cooling systems to the device. The device is represented in the setup by the resistor with various power dissipation values.

2 Experimental Procedure

A setup for transient magnetocaloric cooling was designed and assembled. A schematic diagram of the device and the magnetocaloric cooled resistor cell are presented in **Fig. 2**. An electromagnet (EM) was used as the magnetic field source. The magnetic field change was provided by changing the current supplied to the EM with a slew rate limit of 10 A s^{-1} , reaching a maximum field of 16 kOe. The magnetocaloric material (MCM), which is Gd (Alfa Aesar, 99.99%; 11x11x14mm; 10.41 g) was placed in contact with the thermocouple (Type T bare wires, model number: TT-T-36; 36 AWG, $\phi = 0.13 \text{ mm}$; Neoflon-PFA insulation), denoted as *tc3* in **Fig. 2**, and another thermocouple with the same specs (denoted as *tc1*) was also placed in contact with a thick-film planar resistor (BPC10-100J; 10Ω ; standard tolerance; 27.7x25.4x2.54mm) and Gd. Another thermocouple (denoted as *tc2*) was placed in contact only with the resistor. The resistor and *tc1* were connected to a temperature controller which was then connected to the EM power supply. To perform data acquisition, a USB-serial-I/O adaptor was used to communicate the commands written in LabView 8.5 to the temperature controller. The software performed conversion from thermocouple voltage to temperature. The other thermocouples, *tc2* and *tc3*, which recorded the temperatures of the resistor and Gd were connected to a temperature logger.

The results of the time dependence of temperature, magnetic field and power dissipation the setup are presented in **Fig. 3**. The magnetic field (H) was initially increased (**Fig. 3a**). This increase in H resulted in an increase in temperature (**Fig. 3c**) recorded by the interface thermocouple (T_{intf}). H was switched off when H_{max} was attained, leading to a decrease in the temperature measured by *tc2*, T_{intf} (blue curve in **Fig. 3c**). Our results demonstrate the feasibility of using MCE in this setup. The resistor was programmed to heat to 1 W for $\sim 10 \text{ s}$ upon reaching H_{max} , causing a temperature spike (see red curves in **Fig. 3b** and **c**). Switching off H resulted in reduction of T_{intf} and the temperature of the resistor.

Fig 3 Time dependence of the programmed experimental run for MCE cooling demonstration: (a) magnetic field profile, (b) heating profile of the resistor and (c) interfacial temperature measured. Two experiments are shown: without (blue curves) and with (red curves) power dissipated at the resistor.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Variation in magnetic field ramp rates

The variation of H is an important factor in controlling the temperature change of Gd during magnetization or demagnetization due to MCE. During magnetization, heating can be observed due to the MCE of Gd as well as from heating of the electromagnet (EM) coils. As this initial temperature increase is undesirable, the rate of magnetization was optimized to minimize heating from the EM and MCE. With slow ramp rates, MCE heating can be minimized but at the expense of EM heating. The number of steps to increase H is denoted as N_i , with each step having duration of 0.5 s. N_i was varied from 200 to 3000. The difference between initial starting temperature (T_{start}) and that of the N_i^{th} step ($T_{(N_i)}$) was determined ($\Delta T_{(N_i)}$). The ramp rate for decreasing H (demagnetization rate) was also optimized by varying the number of steps while decreasing the magnetic field (N_f). N_f was varied from 14 to 100 steps. The experimental data for different magnetization and demagnetization rates are shown in **Fig. 4a** and **b**, respectively. For simplicity, the plots of number of steps to ramp H versus $\Delta T_{(N_i)}$ and the temperature

measured are presented in **Fig. 4c** and **d** respectively. The lowest $\Delta T_{(N_i)}$ was observed for $N_i = 1000$, which indicates a compromise between the two contributions to heating. To optimize magnetization rates, this value of N_i was used in subsequent experiments. Demagnetization rates were also optimized: the decrease in T_{intf} due to MCE for $N_f \geq 50$ was less abrupt than for $N_f \leq 20$ (**Fig. 4b**) and the lowest T_{intf} was attained with the fastest demagnetization rate (**Fig. 4d**). This is the lowest limit of N_f for the setup due to the slow rate limit in the power supply unit of the EM. Hence, $N_f = 14$ was used as the demagnetization rate.

Fig 4 Variation of the number of steps for optimization of the setup: during (a) magnetization (N_i); (b) demagnetization (N_f), and their influence of on (c) $\Delta T_{(N_i)}$ and (d) $T_{(N_f)}$ obtained at N_f^{th} step.

3.2 Active cooling

The behavior for different configurations was investigated for the following conditions (**Fig. 5**):

- Heating and passive cooling of only the resistor
- Temperature change of the Gd block due to MCE

- Temperature change of the Gd block in contact with resistor during MCE
- Heating and passive cooling of the resistor in contact with Gd block (no MCE)
- Heating and MCE cooling of the resistor in contact with Gd block

The cooling profiles ($T_R(t)_{cooling}$) and temperature behavior of the resistor (T_R) are the main parameters of interest. When 1 W power is supplied to the resistor with only the resistor present in the cell, it is passively cooled to near its starting temperature (T_{start}) within ~ 750 s (**Fig. 5a**). To determine MCE of Gd, only the Gd block was placed in the cell, the temperature profile (T_{Gd}) is presented in **Fig. 5b**. The initial increase in T_{Gd} was due to the heating of Gd during magnetization. Subsequently when Gd demagnetized upon attaining H_{max} , an abrupt decrease in T_{Gd} was observed. T_{Gd} was subsequently observed to return to the starting temperature (T_{start}). The change in temperature (ΔT) of the Gd block was found to be ~ 3.4 °C and this temperature change was achieved in ~ 17 s. With the resistor in contact with Gd, the temperatures of both bodies during the MCE experiment are plotted in **Fig. 5c**. T_R increased initially due to MCE heating of the Gd block during magnetization. When the Gd block was demagnetized, T_R decreased to $\sim T_{start}$ within ~ 82 s, attaining $\Delta T_R = \sim 0.88$ °C. With the same configuration of the cell, passive cooling of the heated resistor for 1 W heating (without MCE of Gd) is shown in Fig 5d. It takes ~ 560 s for the resistor to cool passively to $\sim T_{start}$. For active cooling of the heated resistor (1 W heating) by MCE, it took ~ 87 s for the resistor to cool, showing that MCE can actively cool the resistor (**Fig. 5e**).

Fig. 5 Time dependence of the temperature of: (a) the cooling of the resistor (T_R) pre-heated with 1W (only resistor present), (b) Gd (T_{Gd}) to demonstrate its MCE (only Gd block is present), (c) the temperatures recorded during MCE of Gd (both resistor and Gd are in contact and without heating), (d) the resistor heated with 1W heating (both resistor and Gd are in contact and without MCE) and (e) resistor during cooling (1W heating with MCE of Gd).

3.2.1 Active cooling of resistor

To study active cooling of various power dissipations of the resistor, the difference between $T_{R(max)}$ and T_R , denoted as ΔT_R , was plotted against time in **Fig. 6** for various heating dissipations of the resistor (1-5 W). Active cooling rate of the resistor by MCE (green curves) showed steeper slopes than those of passive cooling (red curves). For 1 W heating of the resistor, the time taken to cool the resistor was reduced ~85% by MCE active cooling (**Fig. 6a**). For 3 W heating, it requires ~45 s and ~95 s to attain $\Delta T_R = 1.03$ °C for cooling the resistor actively by MCE and passively, respectively (**Fig. 6b**), a ~53% faster cooling rate due to MCE cooling. In addition, MCE cooling achieves $\Delta T_R = 1.42$ °C in ~95 s. For 5 W heating, the resistor

passively cools by $\Delta T_R = 3.95$ °C within ~ 407 s (**Fig. 6c**). A similar magnitude of ΔT_R was attained in ~ 65 s for MCE cooling, which was $\sim 84\%$ faster. Moreover, MCE cooling resulted in a ΔT_R equal to 4.25 °C in ~ 132 s.

Fig 6 Time dependence of ΔT_R for: (a) 1W, (b) 3W and (c) 5W heating of the resistor.

3.2.2 Modeling

From the configuration of the setup assembly of the resistor and Gd, assuming that the assembly was well insulated, it can be considered that heat from the resistor is transferred to Gd in one direction (yellow region in **Fig. 2**). The heat flow from the resistor to Gd can be described by Fourier's Law:

$$\left(\frac{dQ}{dt}\right)_{cond} = -\frac{k_T A}{d} \Delta T \quad (1)$$

where k_T is the thermal conductivity, A is surface area, d is thickness. k_T was assumed to be the effective thermal conductivity between the resistor, Gd and the thermocouple.

The heat modeled by the resistor and the MCE heating of Gd will change the temperature of Gd and the resistor, this temperature change depends on the specific heat capacity(c_p) and mass (m):

$$dQ = mc_p dT. \quad (2)$$

Substituting Eqs. (1) and (2):

$$C_p \frac{dT}{dt} = -k \frac{A}{l} \Delta T = -k \frac{A}{l} (T - T_f)$$

$$\frac{dT}{(T - T_f)} = -k \frac{A}{lC_p} dt$$

$$T(t) - T_f = (T_{R(\max)} - T_f) e^{-k \frac{A}{lC_p} t} = (T_{R(\max)} - T_f) e^{-Kt} \quad (3)$$

Eq. 3 shows that T_R should decrease exponentially to a final temperature (T_f) which is dependent on an experimental constant (K). This constant is a combination of materials properties (thermal conductivity, c_p and geometry), thermal properties of the resistor and Gd.

The experimental $T_R(t)$ data for the cooling profile of the resistor for different power dissipation is shown in **Fig. 7**. The profile of the passively cooled resistor with heat pulse of 1 W (**Fig 7a**) could be matched with Eq. 3 for $K = 0.0027 \text{ s}^{-1}$. A similar exponential fit to (**Eq. 3**) is observed for active cooling profiles of heated resistor by MCE in **Fig. 5b - 5d**. Similar values of K were determined for different power inputs (1, 3 and 5 W in **Fig 5b, 5c** and **5d** respectively), showing the validity of the above model. This is in agreement with the previously observed steeper slopes in the $\Delta T_R(t)$ plots for active cooling. The faster cooling rate of the resistor due to active cooling by MCE demonstrates the capability of MCE for active cooling applications.

Fig 7 (a) Passive cooling profile of resistor upon a power input of 1W and active cooling by MCE upon different heating powers: (b) 1W, (c) 3W and (d) 5W.

The examples of applications in microelectronics for the power loads used in the experimental setup are light emitting devices (LED), Zener diodes, audio amplifiers, and high-brightness diodelaser devices used in communications, industry and medicine. In addition, according to the **Eq. 1**, heat transfer is directly correlated to the cross-sectional area while it is inversely proportional to the thickness of the material. Hence, it is evident that more Gd material is necessary for larger heat loads. To maintain good heat transfer, only the cross-sectional area of the Gd refrigerant material should be increased. An estimation of the scaling up of the system for higher heat loads is shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1 Estimated requirements of Gd refrigerant material for scaled up systems with higher heat loads

Heat load (W)	Required cross-sectional area, A (mm ²)	Calculated			Proposed			Mass of Gd (g)
		Length, L (mm)	Width, W (mm)	A (mm ²)	Length, L (mm)	Width, W (mm)	A (mm ²)	
5 (experiment)	154	14	11	154	14	11	154	10.41 (experiment)
30	924	34.3	27.0	926.1	35	27	945	63.9
50	1540	44.4	34.9	1550	44	35	1540	104.1

4 Conclusions

A proof-of-concept setup demonstrating transient cooling by exploiting the magnetocaloric effect of Gd was designed and developed. Active cooling of thermal spikes of a resistor within one cycle using Gd as the magnetocaloric material was demonstrated.

- ~ 85 % faster cooling rate of the thermal spike of a resistor was achieved by active cooling by MCE compared to passive cooling for 1 W power heating. For power dissipation values of 3W, the resistor was actively cooled ~ 53 % faster, while a cooling rate of ~ 84 % faster was attained for power dissipation of 5 W.
- The rate constant for passive cooling was found to be smaller than that for active cooling, in agreement with theory.
- Our results show that MCE cooling can be an efficient solution to cool thermal spikes.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the US Asian office of Aerospace Research and Development (AOARD), Tokyo Office, AOARD-10-4094, program manager, Dr. K. Caster, the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation and EU FEDER (Project MAT 2010-20537), the PAI of the Regional Government of Andalucía (Project P10-FQM-6462) and the United States Office of Naval Research (Project N00014-11-1-0311).

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